

NUMERICAL STUDY OF THE DRAG FORCE REDUCTION AND HEAT TRANSFER CHARACTERISTICS AROUND A HEATED SQUARE CYLINDER BY USING THREE PARALLEL PARTITIONS

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ABSTRACT: This work introduces a numerical investigation of the fluid flow and thermal convection phenomena using the double multiple relaxation time of the lattice Boltzmann method (DMRT-LBM). The work concentrates on the simulation of the fluid flow and the isotherms lines around the heated square cylinder controlled by three-flat plates placed side by side in a bidimensional channel at a fixed Reynolds number ($Re=150$). The inclusion of the plates is to control the vortex shedding and improve the characteristics of the heat transfer around the squares cylinder. The numerical code is validated with the numerical and experimental results available in the literature for flow past around a square cylinder with and without a control instrument. The influence of the position of the flat plates on the streamlines, the isotherms lines, the drag and lift forces are studied. The results obtained show the inclusion of the partitions decreases the drag force and the lift fluctuate and allows for regular heat exchange.

.Keywords: Lattice Boltzmann method, heat transfer, heated square cylinder, flat plates, Passive Control, Thermal exchange, Fluid flow, Drag force.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, much research has been done to address the physical problems associated with the flow of fluids and heat transfers, and more particularly with heat transfer and the suppression of vortices around one or more bluffing bodies [1-3]. This research is the subject of many practical engineering applications, such as aeronautical, submarine, automotive flows, heat exchanger systems, electronic cooling, gas turbine blades, etc. Thus, many experimental and numerical studies have been conducted to understand the behavior of these physical phenomena in order to know how to control them. These studies deal with fluid flow and heat transfer around one or more blocks of different geometric shapes (square, circle, cylinder, etc.) with or without control tools. One of these studies existing in the literature, we mention those, which have worked on the flow around a single block [4-6]. In addition, little research has been done on the study of the coupling between fluid flow and heat transfer around a controlled block [7-9].

The effect of the position of the control plates on the streamlines, on the isotherms, and the temporal variation of the drag coefficient for a fixed length of the plates ($L_p = 1D$) is realized. The numerical approach to be adopted to make the simulations is the method of Boltzmann Multiple Relaxation Time Lattice (DMRT-LBE)

This article is organized as follows. Firstly, a brief description of the numerical method is given in the second chapter, in which we mention the models D2Q9 and D2Q5 to deal with the flow field and the temperature field respectively. Then the configuration of the studied physical problem and the boundary conditions implemented are described in chapter III. The fourth chapter is reserved for the results showing the validation of the numerical code. Chapter V is devoted to the numerical results obtained representing the effect of the position of the plates on the flow structures, on the isotherms, and the drag coefficient. The final section presents the main conclusions drawn from the discussion of the results.

2. NUMERICAL SCHEME

The lattice Boltzmann method is the numerical approach adopted for the simulation of this physical phenomenon studied in this paper.

Two models are widely used for this method, the LBM a single relaxation time (BGK-SRT) model [13, 14], and the multiple relaxation time (MRT) model [15-18]. In this paper, the MRT model is used since it is more stable, precise, and presents a good convergence compared to the SRT model.

2.1 The D2Q9 model

Thanks to reasons of convergence and compatibility with the model used in thermic, the D2Q9 model was used to treat the distribution of the density of fluid particles. This model is illustrated in figure 1. For more information see my previous work [8, 9].

2.2 The D2Q5 model

For reasons of compatibility and reduction of calculation time, the D2Q5 model is used to treat the thermal problem. The motion of the fluid particles, in this model (D2Q5), is carried out by the discrete velocities which are given by [8,9]:

Figure 1. D2Q9 and D2Q5 model for the velocity and temperature field

4. CONFIGURATION DESCRIPTION AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

3.1 Configuration domain and initial conditions

Figure 2 presents the computational domain geometry for flow past a square cylinder placed in a horizontal bidimensional channel followed by a dual control partition. The square cylinder is placed in an upstream distance $L_u = 6D$ and a downstream length sufficiently large $L_d = 30D$, and a height $H = 11D$ (see Figure 2) where the "D" represents the size of the square cylinder. The controlling partitions are arranged successively downstream the principal square cylinder, having the same length "Lp" and height "h=0.02D". Moreover, g designates the gap spacing between the square cylinder and partitions (see Figure 2). The fluid enters with a dimensionless temperature $\theta_c = -0,5$ and the block is considered heated with a dimensionless temperature $\theta_h = 0,5$. While the walls of the channel are assumed to be adiabatic.

Figure 2. The structure of the computational domain

At the inlet of the channel, the flow is completely developed with a parabolic velocity profile ($u = 1.5 * U_{max} (1 - (y/H)^2)$; $v = 0$) where y is the vertical distance from the centreline, and U_{max} is the maximal entrance velocity of the flow and U and V are the components of velocity vectors. Likewise, at the outlet, the parabolic velocity profile is imposed and the velocity and pressure gradients are considered to be zero.

3.2 Boundary conditions

In LBM, the most well-known type of boundary conditions in the literature, are the Bounce-Back boundary conditions [19]. In the inlet and outlet of the computational domain, the flow is fully developed with a parabolic velocity profile, so the implementation of the boundary conditions of Zou and He is the most preferred [20].

For the thermal problem, Mezrhab *et al.* [21] are proposed a method for treating the heat flux boundary conditions. This method is based on the necessity to move from the macroscopic scale to the mesoscopic scale by using the general term of the distribution function g_i . For more information see the reference [21]. While the walls of the channel are assumed to be adiabatic.

5. VALIDATION

In this paper, we have mentioned several validation cases with several researchers and for different geometries. First, we validated our numerical code with the work of Breuer *et al* [5] where we studied the flow around a cylinder of square

cross-section mounted inside a horizontal channel with a blocking ratio of 1/8.

Fig. 3 shows that our results are generally in good agreement with those of Breuer[5]. The negligible differences between the two results may be due to the mesh size used or the thermal effects treated in our simulation.

Figure 3. the plot validation of the drag coefficient without control

Next, we validated our numerical results with those found numerically by Islam *et al* [6] and Turki *et al* [22] or experimentally by Okajima [23] for a flow around a square obstacle controlled by a single flat plate. Figure 4 shows the variation of the mean value of the drag coefficient as a function of the spacing between the square block and the control plate. A good agreement is observed between our results and the reference results.

Figure 4. the plot validation of the drag coefficient for a single control partition.

6. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the effect of the location of the control partitions on hydrodynamic parameters such as flow patterns, isotherms, and on the mean and temporal drag coefficient are studied. To avoid the effect of the length of the plates, we fixed its length $L_p = 1D$. Similarly, the Reynolds number has been fixed at 150.

5-1. Structures of the streamlines and isotherms.

First, a study on the effect of position on flow control was performed. Figure 5 shows the flow and isotherm contours around the square cylinder, heated and controlled by three parallel partitions located upstream. From this figure (fig.5) an alternating Van Karman vortex street is observed in the wake region downstream of the square cylinder. However, it is observed that the wake is more undulated in the attached case (where the control partitions are connected to the square cylinder). This waviness decreases with increasing gap spacing until a critical position of the partitions ($g = 1.5$). After this crucial position, the wake becomes more and wavier with increasing gap spacing.

Similarly, the size of vortices shedding behind the square cylinder decreases with increasing gap spacing until $g_{critical} = 1,5$ where the vortices have small sizes. The size of the released vortices starts to increase after the critical distance with the increase of the gap spacing. Also, we observe that the number of released vortices behind the square cylinder is also different: 8 vortices appear in the wake region downstream of the square cylinder in the case where the partitions are attached while 6 or 7 vortices appear in the case where the partitions are detached. The frontal surface of the cylinder is exposed directly to the incoming fluid in the uncontrolled case. While in the case where there are three control partitions, the incoming fluid first meets with the partitions. This will decrease the fluidic forces acting on the square cylinder. In the case where the partitions are linked to the block, the incoming fluid has a direct impact on a part of the front face of the cylinder (exposed face), while the other part is controlled by the three partitions. Thus, in the case where g varies from $g = 1$ to $g = 2$ (tested case: $g = 1; 1.3; 1.5; 1.7; 2$) the spacing between the square cylinder and the control partitions is small. In this case, the fluid considers the whole (square cylinder + three partitions) as a single bluff body. The shear layers produced by the edges of the partitions rise to the top and bottom or jump behind the square cylinder. This decreases the number and size of vortices released behind the square cylinder (the fluidic forces acting on the square cylinder also decrease). However, if the spacing is greater ($g > 2$), the shear layers partially or completely strike the front face of the square cylinder, which again increases the pressure forces acting on this face.

Figure 5. Streamlines & Isotherms contours visualisation :

5-2. Drag force

In this section, a study was performed on the time average drag force acting on the square cylinder.

Figure 7 shows the relationship between the time-averaged drag coefficient $C_{d_{mean}}$ and the location of the control partitions while fixing the length of the partitions.

Figure 6 shows the time variation of the drag coefficient without controls with the same grid. From this figure, we find that the average value of the drag coefficient is $C_{d_{mean0}} = 1,1$. A comparison between these two figures (fig 6 and 7) shows that the drag acting on the cylinder decreases strongly when the control partitions are implemented. This diminution of the average value of this coefficient (drag reduction) is due to the modification of the flow entrance striking the square cylinder. In this work, the control partitions are situated upstream of the cylinder, so the cylinder will be in the wake of the partitions. This will decrease the pressure forces applied in this wake area, resulting in a decrease in drag force (and also an increase in lift force).

Figure6. The plot of drag coefficient without control

Similarly, the graph in Figure 7 confirms the discussion of the streamline and isotherm results. The graph shows the highest C_{dmean} value for the case where the partitions are attached to the square cylinder and then a reduction in C_{dmean} values is observed until it reaches a minimum in the case where the control partitions are placed at a distance $g=1.5$. At this critical location, an effective vortex suppression was observed (fig 5-a₂). After this critical location, the drag coefficient increases again with increasing gap spacing. The front face of the square cylinder is partially or completely exposed to the shear layers relieved by the edges of the control partitions. This increases the pressure forces acting on the cylinder and consequently the increase in drag force. The optimal position of the control partitions ($g=1.5$) corresponds to a minimum value of C_{dmean} and to high and regular heat exchange. A maximum reduction of the average drag coefficient reaches about 56% for $g=1.5$ (critical spacing).

Figure 8 shows the temporal variation of the drag coefficient for different positions of the control partitions. From this figure, we can see that the decoupling frequency of the vortices shedding behind the cylinder in the case where the partitions are attached and in the case where the partitions are very spaced is very higher than in the case where the partitions are located close to the cylinder ($g=1$; 1.3; 1.5; 1.7; 2). This is due to the interaction between the incoming fluid and the square cylinder (case where $g=0$ and $g=4$). Therefore, in the other cases (g varies from 1 to 2) the incoming fluid considers the control partitions and the cylinder as a single bluff body. This decreases the fluidic forces acting on the cylinder as well as the amplitude of the lost vortices.

Figure7. The average drag coefficient in the function of the gap spacing

Figure8. The temporal drag coefficient visualization

CONCLUSION

In this research, a numerical investigation was performed to study the vortex suppression (drag reduction) and to study the heat transfer characteristics on a heated square cylinder placed in a horizontal 2D channel and controlled by three partitions arranged in parallel upstream of the square cylinder.

The numerical results obtained show that the drag acting on the square cylinder reduces in all the cases studied compared to the uncontrolled case. This shows the importance and the necessity of flow control. The maximum reduction of the drag is observed in the case where the spacing between the square cylinder and the partitions becomes a critical space $g_{critical}=1.5$. At this spacing, large and regular heat exchange is observed. Also, the size of the thermal vortices and the width of the Von Karman street decreases at this critical position. Therefore, for beneficial use of the control partitions, for example, in the cooling of electronic components, it is preferable to use three parallel partitions placed upstream of the square cylinder at a critical distance $g=1,5$

REFERENCES

- [1] Monat, J. P., & Gannon, T. F. Applying systems thinking to engineering and design. Systems, vol. 6, no 3, p. 34, 2018.
- [2] Manshoor, B. B., Nicolleau, F. C. G. A., Beck, S. B. M. "The fractal flow conditioner for orifice plate flow meters". Flow Measurement and Instrumentation, vol. 22, no 3, pp. 208-214, 2011.
- [3] Harte, R., & Van Zijl, G. P. Structural stability of concrete wind turbines and solar chimney towers exposed to dynamic wind action. Journal of Wind engineering and industrial aerodynamics, vol. 95, no 9-11, p. 1079-1096, 2007.
- [4] Moussaoui, M.A, Jami, M., Mezrhab, A., Naji, H.: MRT-Lattice Boltzmann simulation of forced convection in a plane channel with an inclined square cylinder. International Journal of Thermal Sciences 49: 131–142, 2010.
- [5] M. Breuer, J. Bernsdorf, T. Zeiser, F. Durst, Accurate computations of the laminar flow past a square cylinder based on two different methods: lattice Boltzmann and finite-volume, Int. J. Heat Fluid Flow, Vol. 21 (2), 186-196, 2000.

- [6] S. Ul. Islam, S.U. Rahman, H. Abbasi, W.S. Shahina, T. Lattice Boltzmann study of wake structures and force statistics for various gap spacings between a square rod with a detached flat plate. *Arab. J. Sci. Eng.* 2015, 40, 2169–2182.
- [7] Nazeer, G.: Numerical investigation of different flow regimes for multiple staggered rows. *AIP Advances*, Vol. 9, no 3, pp. 035247, 2019.
- [8] Y. Admi, M. A. Moussaoui, A. Mezrhab, V. Botton, D. Henry "Convective heat transfer past a three side-by-side square cylinders using double MRT- lattice Boltzmann method" *Journal Mechanics and Industry*, 2019.
- [9] Y. Admi, M. A. Moussaoui and A. Mezrhab, "Effect of a flat plate on heat transfer and flow past a three side-by-side square cylinders using double MRT-lattice Boltzmann method," 2020 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Electronics, Control, Optimization and Computer Science (ICECOCS), Kenitra, Morocco, 2020, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICECOCS50124.2020.9314506.
- [10] Noël, R., Ge, F., Zhang, Y., Navarro, L., Courbebaisse, G. Lattice Boltzmann method for modelling of biological phenomena. In: 25th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO). IEEE, p. 2654-265, 2017.
- [11] Naughton, N. M., & Georgiadis, J. G. Lattice Boltzmann method for simulation of diffusion magnetic resonance imaging physics in heterogeneous tissue models. arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.00908, 2019
- [12] Guo, S., Feng, Y., Jacob, J., Renard, F., & Sagaut, P. An efficient lattice Boltzmann method for compressible aerodynamics on D3Q19 lattice. *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 418, p. 109570, 2020.
- [13] P.L. Bhatnagar, E.P. Gross, M. Krook, A model for collision processes in gases. I. Small amplitude processes in charged and neutral one-component systems. *Physical Review Letters*, Vol.94, pp.511–525, 1954.
- [14] Lallemand P, Luo LS. Theory of the lattice Boltzmann method: dispersion, dissipation, isotropy, Galilean invariance, and stability. *Physical Review Letters E* 2000; 61:6546–6562.
- [15] Moussaoui, M. A., Admi, Y., Lahmer, E. B., & Mezrhab, A. Numerical investigation of convective heat transfer in fluid flow past a tandem of triangular and square cylinders in channel. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 1091, No. 1, p. 012058). IOP Publishing, 2021.
- [16] Moussaoui, M.A., Lahmer E.B., Admi Y., Mezrhab A., Natural convection heat transfer in a square enclosure with an inside hot block, *International Conference on Wireless Technologies, Embedded and Intelligent Systems, WITS 2019, IEEE*.
- [17] Lahmer, E.B., Moussaoui M.A., Mezrhab A., Investigation of laminar flow and convective heat transfer in a constricted channel based on double MRT-LBM, *International Conference on Wireless Technologies, Embedded and Intelligent Systems, WITS 2019, IEEE*.
- [18] J. Benhamou, M. Jami, A. Mezrhab, V. Botton, D. Henry. Numerical study of natural convection and acoustic waves using the lattice Boltzmann method, *heat Transfer*, Vol. 49, pp.3779–3796, 2020.
- [19] M. Bouzidi, M. Firdaouss, P. Lallemand, Momentum transfer of a Boltzmann lattice fluid with boundaries, *Physics of Fluids*, Vol.13, no.11, pp. 3452-3459, 2001.
- [20] Q. Zou, X. He, on pressure and velocity boundary conditions for the lattice Boltzmann BGK model, *Physics of Fluids*, Vol.9, no.6, pp. 1591-1598, 1997.
- [21] Mezrhab, A., Moussaoui, M.A. Jami, M., Naji, H., Bouzidi, M.: Double MRT thermal lattice Boltzmann method for simulating convective flows, *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 374, pp. 3499–3507, 2010.
- [22] Turki, S. Numerical simulation of passive control on vortex shedding behind square cylinder using splitter plate. *Eng. Appl. Comput. Fluid Mech.* 2, 514–524 (2008).
- [23] Okajima, A.: Strouhal numbers of rectangular cylinders. *J. Fluid Mech.* 123, 379–398, 1982.